

Influence of 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid on photoluminescence property of Gd³⁺ doped fluorapatite

Kranthi Kumar Gangu^a, Raviraj Vankayala^b, Anima S. Dadhich^a and Mukkamala Saratchandra Babu^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, GITAM University, Visakhapatnam-530 045, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : mscbabu@yahoo.com Fax : 91-891-2790032

^bDepartment of Chemistry, National Tsing Hua University, Hsinchu 30013, Taiwan

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Abstract : Gd³⁺ doped fluorapatite (FAP) had been prepared hydrothermally at 160 °C in presence of an additive, 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid (BTCA). Morphology, phase and photoluminescence properties of samples were characterized by powder X-ray diffraction, FT-IR, SEM and fluorescence spectroscopy. Polycrystalline FAP : Gd³⁺ powder transformed to rod shaped crystals with influence of BTCA. After photoexcitation at 260 nm, FAP : Gd³⁺ emitted ultraviolet emissions at 357 nm and 395 nm. Photoluminescent intensity of FAP : Gd³⁺ diminished with increasing concentration of BTCA.

Keywords : Morphology, fluorapatite, additive, photoluminescence.

Introduction

Calcium apatites, [Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH/F/Cl)₂], has drawn great attention due to their prominent role in many biomedical applications due to their biocompatible and osteoconductive properties¹⁻⁷. Among calcium apatite family, fluorapatite (FAP) is considered as an active bio-material due to its low solubility and good biocompatibility^{8,9}. The release of fluoride ions from fluorapatites is known to hamper the bacterial metabolism¹⁰⁻¹². The crystal structure of apatite is flexible to accommodate various monovalent, divalent and multivalent ions such as Na⁺, Pb²⁺, Ln³⁺, Bi³⁺ etc. in the site of Ca²⁺ with minor alterations in the symmetry¹³. Doping of lanthanide ions to apatite is facilitated due to similar radius to Ca²⁺ ions as well as high affinity to PO₄³⁺ ions¹⁴. Fluorapatite (FAP) has a hexagonal structure, where the unit cell contains two formula units of [Ca₅(PO₄)₃X]. The Gd³⁺ ion occupies the Ca²⁺ or Ca²⁺ and F⁻ sites in the FAP¹⁵ as suggested below :

Calcium apatites doped with trivalent lanthanide are used as fluorescent probes due to their eccentric lumines-

cent properties¹⁴. Gadolinium is one of the important rare-earth element used as a contrast agent for Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT). So doping of Gd³⁺ into apatite has great advantage for biomedical applications¹⁷.

Hydrothermal synthesis is one of the promising techniques to prepare good crystalline apatites compared to other synthetic routes such as mechano synthesis, co-precipitation, sol-gel process, and microwave irradiation. The soluble organic molecules play an important role as additives to controls the shape and size of growing inorganic crystals^{18,19}.

Herein, we report the morphology and luminescence properties of Gd³⁺ doped fluorapatite (FAP) prepared in presence of 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid (BTCA).

Results and discussion

Morphology :

Fig. 1, shows the SEM images of the Gd³⁺ doped fluorapatite (FAP) obtained in the absence and presence of additive, 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid (BTCA). Polycrystalline FAP : Gd³⁺ was obtained in absence of

BTA (Fig. 1a). The variable sizes of rods about 200–300 nm length and 20–50 nm width had resulted in presence of BTA. Role of BTCA in influencing the transformation of polycrystalline FAp : Gd³⁺ to nano rods cannot be ruled out (Figs. 1b, 1c and 1d). No significant change in size and morphology of rods of FAp : Gd³⁺ was ob-

Fig. 1. SEM images of FAp : Gd³⁺ obtained (a) absence BTCA, (b) 1.25 mmol BTCA, (c) 2.5 mmol BTCA and (d) 5.0 mmol BTCA.

served in presence of variable concentrations of BTCA. The incorporation of gadolinium (Gd³⁺) into the nano rods was evident from the EDAX spectrum (Fig. 2). EDAX analysis reveals that, Gd³⁺ concentration in FAp was 58.6 wt% in the absence of BTCA. But the dopant con-

centration progressively decreased to 33.6, 3.7 and 0.5 wt% on increasing BTCA concentration to 1.25 mmol, 2.5 mmol and 5.0 mmol, respectively. This may be due to more affinity of COO⁻ groups of BTCA towards Gd³⁺ over Ca²⁺.

Fig. 3 shows that the Powder XRD patterns of FAp : Gd³⁺ produced in presence of BTCA is similar to pure HAp and agrees with the standard hexagonal phase of Ca₅(PO₄)₃F (ICSD reference code : 98-008-1442). After doping Gd³⁺ into FAp the intensity of peaks decreased with decreasing dopant concentration (Figs. 3b and 3d). The additional peaks at 12.5°, 20.4° and 36.5° are attributed to the BTCA molecules adsorbed on the surface of FAp (Figs. 3c and 3d).

The FT-IR spectra of FAp : Gd³⁺ is shown in Fig. 4. A broad absorption bands in the range of 3000–3500 cm⁻¹ are assigned to O-H vibrations from water molecules. The characteristic vibrational frequencies of asymmetric stretching peaks at 1098, 1032 and asymmetric bending peaks at 605, 504 cm⁻¹ correspond to P-O bond. The additional characteristic peak at 1554 cm⁻¹ corresponds to carboxylate groups of BTCA (Figs. 4c and 4d).

Effect of dopant on photoluminescent properties of FAp : Gd³⁺ :

The emission spectrum of the Gd³⁺ doped FAp is shown in Fig. 5. Two emission peaks at 357 and 395 nm were observed after photoexcitation of sample at 260 nm.

Fig. 2. EDAX analysis of FAp : Gd³⁺ obtained (a) absence BTCA, (b) 1.25 mmol BTCA, (c) 2.5 mmol BTCA and (d) 5.0 mmol BTCA.

Fig. 3. PXRD patterns of FAp : Gd³⁺ obtained (a) absence BTCA, (b) 1.25 mmol BTCA, (c) 2.5 mmol BTCA and (d) 5.0 mmol BTCA.

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectrum of FAp : Gd³⁺ obtained (a) absence BTCA, (b) 1.25 mmol BTCA, (c) 2.5 mmol BTCA and (d) 5.0 mmol BTCA.

Fig. 5. Photoluminescence spectrum of FAp : Gd^{3+} obtained (a) absence BTCA, (b) 1.25 mmol BTCA, (c) 2.5 mmol BTCA and (d) 5.0 mmol BTCA.

Unfilled $4f$ shell of Gd^{3+} ion has seven unpaired electrons and are shielded by $5s$ and $5p$ orbitals. Among triply ionized lanthanide elements, Gd^{3+} shows unique character and displays several emissions in ultraviolet region which are useful in phototherapy treatment to cure skin diseases²⁰. Peaks at 357 and 395 nm correspond to $f-f$ transitions of Gd^{3+} ion¹⁶. The photoluminescence intensity decreased with increasing concentration BTCA i.e. decrease of Gd^{3+} ions concentration (Figs. 2a and 5a). It was observed that maximum amount (%wt) of Gd^{3+} could be doped into FAp in the absence of BTCA and exhibited highest intensity (Fig. 2a). Progressive decrease in luminescence intensity was observed on gradually increasing the concentration of BTCA. At 5.0 mmol BTCA, the concentration of Gd^{3+} dopant was only 0.5 wt% in the FAp and hence it exhibited very low emission intensity (Fig. 4d).

Experimental

Materials :

All reagents were of analytical grade and used without any further purification. $Ca(NO_3)_3 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Na_3PO_4 \cdot 12H_2O$ and NaF were purchased from Merck, India. $Gd(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ and 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

Synthesis :

2.5 mmol of $Ca(NO_3)_3 \cdot 4H_2O$ and 0.025 mmol of $Gd(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ were dissolved in 25 mL deionized water. Varying amounts (1.25 mmol/2.5 mmol/5.0 mmol)

of 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid (BTCA) was added to the above solution and stirred for 15 min at room temperature. 25 mL of solution containing 0.5 mmol of NaF and 1.5 mmol of $Na_3PO_4 \cdot 12H_2O$ was added dropwise to the previous solution and stirred further at room temperature for 30 min. The mixed solution was finally transferred into a Teflon lined autoclave and heated at 160 °C for 12 h. The obtained precipitate was washed with deionized water several times and dried at 60 °C.

Characterization :

Morphology of the FAp was examined by scanning electron microscope (SEM) using JSM-5510, JEOL equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectrum. Phase identification was performed using Powder X-ray diffractometer, Panalytical, X-PertPro system, with $Cu-K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15405$ nm). The FT-IR spectrum of the sample was recorded on Perkin-Elmer, Spectrum-2. The photoluminescence spectrum of the solid sample was recorded with "Perkin-Elmer LS-55 Luminescence Spectrometer" at room temperature.

Conclusions

Gd^{3+} doped fluorapatite (FAp) was synthesized hydrothermally in presence of additive, 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid (BTCA). Gd^{3+} ions doped FAp emitted ultraviolet luminescence at 357 nm and 395 nm. BTCA influenced the formation of rod shaped FAp and also reduced the photoluminescence intensity by complexing the Gd^{3+} ions. FAp : Gd^{3+} may prove to be a very useful material for treatment of skin diseases as well as potential applicant in biological labelling.

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